

A SWOT Analysis to Improve Quality Management System in Education: A Case Study in UTYCC

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Abstract

In this paper, the need and requirements of a Quality Management System (QMS) for Education are analyzed by SWOT to support our University's Educational Organization are described. This paper is an attempt to present why the QMS system in education and its new look of ISO 21001:2018 should be associated as the prime management system of our University of Technology (Yatanarpon Cyber City) (UTYCC). The study undertakes a SWOT analysis and also discusses what role the QMS System can play in the growth of these entities. All the activities are aimed at helping outstanding students and promoting the quality of academic staff to improve their communication skills in customer focus and competence that the resources needed for our Educational Organizations. This research aims to analyze and understand the dynamics of educational organizations based on ISO 21001:2018 to our UTYCC's quality education. The method used in this research is based on continual improvement of the QMS system in ISO 9001:2015 in UTYCC and checked by SWOT Analysis. For this research, the data collection is done by using interviews, observations, and documentation control which is obtained from accurate information about the internal auditing being conducted. Overall, the benefits of implementation results by QMS system with the highlight of ISO 21001:2018 in Educational Organizations are described. More significantly, in this paper, a clear discussion of Strong, Weak, Opportunities, and Treat based on our QMS system, carried out the challenges from this analysis, and shaped the future plan for our UTYCC.

Keywords: *Education, ISO 9001:2015, ISO 21001:2018, SWOT, QMS System*

1. INTRODUCTION

Our surroundings have various challenges. In this day and age, the development of digital technology era dominates all areas of our lives. So, we are required to be able to survive and to be able to compete. This phenomenon can also be applied to non-profit organizations such as education. There are many challenges in improving the quality of education, infrastructure development, getting new students and good teachers, and various other competitions. Therefore, our institution leaders must implement ISO 9001:2015 management system to play a vital role in improving the quality of educational institutions.

Our university always needs to improve the implementation of quality education. The expectation of quality education is one of the necessary and beautiful structures for our governance. So, each component of our university is on one road and must work together to complete its obligations as the quality management system of the education unit to achieve our goals. The strategy for this improvement is inseparable from the management of quality or

continual quality improvement at our university. To achieve goals or "ways to achieve ends", in our educational management, we must make strategies that can be obtained or known through the help of SWOT analysis. [1] and [4].

Furthermore, our university is expected to be able to see the various opportunities that exist in order to develop its educational institutions and to answer the challenges of its internal and external environment. Thus, by looking at the university's risks and opportunities, we are interested in conducting research by employing SWOT analysis and its implementation strategies in QMS systems in education. The purposes of this study were to analyze, describe SWOT, and formulate an implementation strategy in QMS systems at our university. Additionally, this study also aims to invent the right implementation strategy in maximizing the excellence or strength factor, utilizing various opportunities, minimizing weaknesses, and overcoming various threats in education at our university.

We review the feedback of teachers' educationists, and managing power, opportunities, and threats will be raised through the curriculum. Thus, this paper deals with the importance of teacher education quality, satisfaction, student outcomes, innovation, teaching competencies skills, etc., and feedback. The discussion will report on the impact of the implementation of the SWOT framework for the improvement of the QMS system in our University (UTYCC). The objective of this paper is to check the implementation of the QMS system of our university using ISO 9001:2015 by ISO 21001:2018 and SWOT analysis. In this way, two powerful management tools are combined to take advantage of the characteristics of both of them.

2. METHOD OF RESEARCH

2.1 Implementation of ISO 9001:2015 in UTYCC

ISO 9001:2015 is being implemented in several technological universities in Myanmar, including our university (UTYCC). Our University has been implementing this QMS system, since 2019 to improve our interactions, under the requirements of the international Standard and intended to fill the needs and expectations of relevant interested parties. We have finished ISO 9001:2015 Re-Certification in 2022. Why we implement this system in our university is to enable the accreditation system to be implemented to achieve international status. It is one of the basic step functions for us to get accreditation.

2.2 Integrating ISO 21001:2018 and ISO 9001:2015 with SWOT Analysis

To improve the effectiveness of the QMS system, we can integrate it with SWOT Analysis. The main mission of our university is to produce quality intellectuals that can develop themselves. As we know, ISO 21001:2018 is a management tool for our Educational Organizations to provide educational products and services to meet the needs and requirements of learners and other customers. It includes the process for the improvement system. It is similar to ISO 9001:2015. This management system can be by applying the criteria and methods such as monitoring, measurement, and related performance indicators to ensure effective operation and control them. The most the fact is evaluating these management processes and implementing any changes that are needed to ensure achieving intended results. These management systems are based on PDCA concepts. To get the international standard, it has designed by the clauses such as policy, planning, implementation and operation, checking and corrective action (performance assessment), management review, and improvement. Risk and opportunity management is undertaken as part of our organization's day-to-day operations. We assign the risk and opportunities to each level in the hierarchy Budgets and profitability,

Performance and efficiency, Resources and targets, and Evaluation and assurance. This shift of focus helps us to understand the customers and suppliers of our university. [4].

2.3 Description of the SWOT Analysis

A SWOT analysis can be carried out for our students, classrooms, university, or teaching staff. It involves specifying the objective of our university and identifying the internal and external factors that are favorable and unfavorable to achieve that objective. [3], [6].

Our strengths mean our positive attributes, tangible and intangible, internal to our organization. All these are within our control. We consider what we do well and what internal resources we have. For strength, we think about the positive attributes of people, such as knowledge, background, education, credentials, network, reputation, or skills—tangible assets of our university, such as credit, existing customers, or our distribution technology. And we also consider what advantages we have over our competition. [2] and [3].

Weaknesses are aspects of our education. It can reduce the value we offer or place us at a competitive disadvantage. So, we need to enhance these areas to compete with our best competitors. In this case, we must know about what areas will need improvement to accomplish our objectives or compete with our strongest competitor and we must also know which factor in our education lacks such as skills or technology.

Opportunities come from external attractive factors. These represent reasons our education is likely to prosper. We must know what opportunities exist in our market or the environment that we can benefit from, the positive perception of our education, and whether there has been recent end-user growth or whether there have been other changes in the market that create an opportunity to exploit to its advantage [2], and [3].

Threats include external factors beyond our control that could place our strategy at risk. We cannot control these, but we may benefit by having contingency plans to address them if they should occur. We must know our existing conditions or potential competitors, which factors beyond our control could place our education at risk, the challenges such as an unfavorable trend or development that may lead to deteriorating our university's ranking, the situations might threaten our efforts, a significant change in supplier, the trend or shifts in consumer behavior, the end users, or government regulations, and a new product or technology and research introduced in the environment that could cause trouble for our university.

Thus, we can use SWOT analysis as an analytical tool for strategic planning and management in our organization to find the most correct strategies to achieve our quality objectives.

2.4 The Algorithm for the Educational Organization

To make a SWOT analysis, we must create six steps such as the following algorithm.

Step 1: We recognize the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats for the education. We evaluate the strategic alternatives from the SWOT matrix.

Step 2: Identifying the strategic objectives by ISO 9001:2015.

Step 3: Monitoring the key performance indicator by QMS System. In our management System, the SWOT's factors, sub-factors, strategic alternatives, and strategic objectives must be considered in it.

Step 4: Auditing for checking the system to control. The pairwise comparisons between the various management of the QMS System are carried out.

Step 5: Performing assessment for customer feedback and risk.

Step 6: Go to step 2. Repeating the Strategic Objectives until either an optimum solution is obtained. Again, identify the Key Performance Indicator (KPI).

3. A SWOT ANALYSIS ON QMS SYSTEM

3.1 Description of the SWOT Matrix at the University

To visually organize the results of a SWOT analysis, we will present the results of the SWOT analysis in the form of a matrix. To display this analysis, we make a **four-quadrant table with each quadrant representing one of the four elements of this analysis [3], and [6]. We use the** visualization technique to show the relationships between the internal and external factors which easier to identify potential strategic actions based on these factors.

We can meet the challenges in our educational surroundings such as the Human resources and Institution capacity cluster, Financial and Investment cluster, Policy and regulatory cluster, External competition and education environment cluster, Decline in volume of students Growing competition in all markets, New types of competitors, etc.

From the analysis of these factors and the survey in our university, we note the SWOT matrix can be shown in Table 1.

Table 1: SWOT Matrix of Our Education

	Strength	Weakness
Opportunities	1-Good relations with suppliers and customers. 2-Good delivery standards. 3-Variety and prices of products 4- Customer Trust 5- Government Trust 6- New Products (ME, Ph.D) 7- Accreditation, International Standard, QMS 8- ERC (30%), plagiarism 9- Joint Program and Partnerships 10- Industrial Linkage 11- IP laws 12--Network Communication	1-Infrastructure: Poor financial management system 2-Human resources 3-Investment Lab 4-Promotions 5-Speed 6-Innovation

Threats	13- Disruptive Competition	7- Cost of Human resource
	14- Old Technology	8- HR limitation & Work Load
	15- Research Laboratory	9- Centralization
	16- University Ranking	10- Marketing Environment
	17- Reserved services	11- Research Fund
		12- Lack of an integrated information system

This table shows that Strengths and Opportunities (**SO**) strategies focus on how our organization can use its strengths to take advantage of the opportunities in the external environment. In this strategy of formulation, the university utilized all of its strengths to seize and utilize the existing various opportunities. Strengths and Threats (**ST**) strategies focus on how the organization can use its strengths to overcome the threats in the external environment. Weaknesses and Opportunities (**WO**) strategies focus on how the organization can overcome its weaknesses to take advantage of the opportunities in the external environment. Thus, this strategy formulation is the strength of this educational institution to overcome the external threats of educational institutions. Weaknesses and Threats (**WT**) strategies focus on how the organization can overcome its weaknesses and reduce the threats in the external environment. This weaknesses-threat formulation can seek to reduce its weaknesses and to stay away from the various threats [1], [2], [3], [4], and [6].

3.2 SWOT Analysis of Staff's Competencies at UTYCC

Our university is implementing the QMS system. By using the SWOT analysis, it is support to check the current situation of our education sector and our staff's competencies. Its importance comes from what we can do with the result of the SWOT analysis. Ten quality objectives (i.e.) ten KPI (as shown in Figure 1) are selected as the improvement areas for our university

From the implementation of QMS system and the auditing in our university, we can remark the SWOT analysis on our management system such as Academic Staff, Administrative personnel, and student satisfaction can be shown in Table 2.

Table 2: SWOT Analysis on Our QMS System

Strength	<p>1-Highly qualified and experienced teaching faculty.</p> <p>2-Most of the faculties departments engaged in research work.</p> <p>3-Most of the faculty members are associated with national and international literary communities and societies.</p> <p>4-Senior faculty members such as heads of departments are attached to the Board of Studies (BOS).</p> <p>5 -Some teaching faculty awarded national and international forms.</p>
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	<p>6 -Some of them lead conferences, workshops, and seminars.</p> <p>7- Able to connect with student’s satisfaction.</p>
Weakness	<p>1- Infrastructure: Poor financial management system</p> <p>2- Gap of experience between senior & young teachers.</p> <p>3- Innovation curriculum flexibility.</p> <p>4- Collaborative team teaching.</p> <p>5- Investment Lab</p>
Opportunities	<p>1-Extracurricular activities facilities are available.</p> <p>2- Personal development opportunity.</p> <p>3- Fieldwork facility.</p> <p>4-Formation of a framework of curriculum.</p> <p>5-Flexible work loads.</p>
Threats	<p>1-Departmental Lab.</p> <p>2-Departmental library.</p> <p>3-Faculty study room.</p> <p>4- Research Fund</p>

Figure 1: KPI results of UTYCC’s QMS system

4. DISCUSSION

During SWOT analysis, the internal factors such as strengths and weaknesses, and external factors such as opportunities and threats are examined. It can be carried out for our students, university, or staff. We can analyze to be fundamental to any proposed risks and opportunities as it is also very important in continual quality improvement. This is because it

can help in restructuring other aspects of education to be adjusted to the current situation. The primary goal of real state analysis is to enable the key performance to identify areas of possible conflict, take note of the weaknesses, and threats, and find out risks and opportunities available [1].

4.1 Role of the Internal Analysis in UTYCC by SWOT-Past and Future

To improve the QMS system in education and identify the organization's needs, we must need to realize the SWOT analysis. After examining this, we realize the internal strengths of our university included as follows: first, a good and transparent university management. It could be indirect that the current integrated management was better and more transparent than on the previous years. This thing had implications for our university's effectiveness and efficiency in service. Second, it was the number of field-practicing students. This school had a program to not only equip students with knowledge but also to let students feeling the aspects of their skills or abilities. Third, our university website and adequate computer facilities must be adequate. Our university already owned a computer laboratory, language laboratory, e-learning system, and learning management system. This would ease our university, especially during the teaching and learning process, access to information, our university's ranking. The fourth strength was the quality of the teacher. The quality of teachers in our university was very professional. Fifth, this school had good graduation statistics in every year.

In weakness possession, first, the infrastructure was inadequate. Our university was having lack of supporting facilities, such as the absence of a school field and sports facilities for students. Second, it was the lack of use of social media for promotion. Third, it was using fewer budgets. This thing, of course, inhibited the performance of the teachers in improving the quality of education. Fourth, there was a gap in experience between senior and young teachers. This thing was also important for improving the quality of education, innovation curriculum flexibility, and collaborative team teaching. The fifth factor was the insufficient teachers. The smaller number of educators and employees at the university could be overloaded. Sixth, alumni were not well coordinated by educational institutions. Seventh, there was minimal collaboration with companies in the marketing sector.

4.2 Role of the External Analysis in UTYCC by SWOT-Past and Future

The opportunity and threat analysis is carried out by examining external factors. The external factors of our university in terms of opportunities were including: First, there was support from the government in the form of funds. It also received educational assistance from the central and regional governments such as scholarships for students' achievements, scholarships for disadvantaged students, BOS, and others. Second, there were end users, companies that needed alumni as their employees. Their field of work was related to marketing business. Third, there were many job opportunities for students when they graduated. They can accept such as graduates who are competent, adaptive, and ready to work. Fourth, the alumni could be seen as an opportunity to build and revive the university. Furthermore, the university could ask for the help of alumni to promote itself. The fifth internal factor was the development of digital technology. The development of digital technology could be employed as an opportunity for UTYCC to do school promotion, to change its teaching and learning styles, to have an education management information system, and so on. Sixth, it was the opening of a part-time diploma or class which was by community needs. At the same time, it should also be able to answer the needs of the community and to fill our university's requirements.

While the threats from this school included the following: First, there were other institutions. This can be made the competition between institutions increasingly tense. Second, the number of students may be decreasing. If the quantity of students which will be decreasing each year, it can make the existence of this university in danger because students are the primary customers in educational institutions. Third, there were employees and school staffs who wanted to resign from this educational institution. Based on the results of the SWOT analysis, for improvement of competence, welfare, and job satisfaction, the position of this university should be applied in the current conditions by changing the management style or method of teaching and learning, building cooperation with marketing companies, coordinating alumni, providing more learning facilities, direct field marketing practices, working together with stakeholders, opening school businesses, and opening new part-time classes which were different from other university and were in accordance with the needs of the local community.

5. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

To become a professional worker, entrepreneur, and can take studies to a higher level, the internal conditions of our university UTYYCC have both strengths and weaknesses. The strength factors of this educational institution that can be seen are as follows: good quality management system of the university, the teacher's ability as the basic source of resources during the teaching and learning process, the direct field practice for students, having a school web and computer laboratory, and having good academics record as an educational institution. While the weaknesses of this educational institution include as follows: inadequate infrastructure; limited and less strategic school space; poor coordination alumni; teacher quantity; less of human resources; minimal coordination with marketing companies; and the lack of school promotion. Both of the above factors (the strengths and weaknesses factors) are the supporting and inhibiting factors for UTYYCC. The external conditions of UTYYCC have both opportunities and threats. The opportunities owned by university could be seen in as follows: government support; a large number of alumni; the development of innovated technology that could be maximized for promotional activities and the implementation of education information systems for institutions; the opening of part-time majors' classes, and the recruitment of new teachers. The threat factor includes the presence of other institutions; educators and employees who want to resign from the school; and lack of support from the government.

Furthermore, the strategy that is in line with the current university position is better to support a QMS system as its approach. UTYYCC should maintain the advantages that it has been possessing. Thus, the internal strengths could improve the quality of education and it could also help to be able to compete well with other universities. This is very important so that it can still exist and survive in the competition. It should also improve their educational management as an institution. In order, to be able to overcome the existing weaknesses, UTYYCC is expected to improve its input, process and output factors. This is considered as very important because the good quality of education could only be achieved if the inputs, processes, and outputs have high quality. UTYYCC has various external opportunities in improving its input, process, and output. Thus, it is expected that UTYYCC could the various opportunities to leverage its educational institutions so it can compete with other institutions such as by coordinating alumni, opening new departments which are fit in with the wider community's need, using web schools and social media for promotion, recruiting educators, and so on.

To bring all of the opportunities into real life, UTYCC is advised to use its maximum power in capturing those opportunities since the existence of the university is currently in risk. The threats are in the form of the followings: the number of students who want to transfer to the other universities each year, staffs who want to resign, and the existence of other institutions. By looking at the previously mentioned threats, UTYCC should immediately look for and change its educational quality management system by utilizing its internal strength minimizing weaknesses, and employing the existing opportunities so that it can exist or survive in competition with other universities.

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REFERENCES

1. Y. B. Keban, S. Arifin, and R. Wahyono, "SWOT Analysis and Its Implementation Strategies in Educational Management", *Journal of Education and Practice* www.iiste.org ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online) (DOI: 10.7176/JEP Vol.10, No.12, 2019), pp. 86-92.
2. Glenn L. Velmonte, "SWOT Analysis Philippine Educational System", *International Journal of Intelligent computing and Technology*, June (2020) Vol.4, Iss.1 pp:18-24.
3. B. G. Dana, "SWOT analysis to improve quality management production", *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 62 (2012) pp. 319-324.
4. E. Wibisono, "The new management system ISO 21001:2018: What and why educational organizations should adopt it," *Proceeding of 11th International Seminar on Industrial Engineering and Management*. ISSN: 1978-774X . pp 66-73
5. G. D. Boca, "SWOT Analyze and e-learning", *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 182 (2015) , pp.10-14
6. K. Das, D. Roy and P. Biswas, "SWOT Analysis of Teacher Educators in B.Ed. Department under West Bengal State University in West Bengal, India," ISSN: 2455-3085 (Online), *RESEARCH REVIEW International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, Volume-04, Issue-06, (June-2019), pp.87-91.
7. Luis E. Quezadaa, "Measuring Performance Using SWOT Analysis and Balanced Scorecard", *Procedia Manufacturing* 39 (2019), pp. 786–793.